

and 1600 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$). The above oxime-*O*-sulphonic acids (1 g) were then kept over neutral alumina (30 g) for 1 h and subjected to chromatography. The eluates from benzene-ether (1 : 1) gave the lactams (3a-c); ν_{max} 3 180 (NH), 1 670, 1 615 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{CONH}$); λ_{max} 220 ($\log \epsilon$ 4.1) (α,β -unsaturated lactam⁶); δ 6.25 (1H, s, NH exchangeable with D_2O), 5.6 (vinyl-H), 3.5 (1H, m, $8\beta\text{-H}$); 3b and 3c δ 4.5 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz, $3\alpha\text{-H}$)⁷.

The ketoximes (2g-i) from the ketones (2a-c) : To a solution of 2a-c (1.5 g) in ethanol (30 ml) hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3.5 g) and sodium acetate (5 g) were added and refluxed for 4 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the remaining solution was poured in ice-cold water to obtain the oxime (2g-i; 1.2 g, 80%) which was recrystallised from ethanol.

Beckmann rearrangement of the ketoximes (2g-i) : To a solution of the ketoxime (2g-i; 1 g) in dry pyridine (15 ml), PTS (1 g) was added and kept at room temperature (30°) for 12 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in ice-cold water to obtain a solid (oxime tosylates). The solid was extracted with ether- CHCl_3 mixture (1 : 1) and the extract was washed with dilute HCl and water and dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous). The removal of solvent yielded light brown semi-solid, which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (30 g, Brockmann grade 1). Elution with petroleum-ether-benzene (1 : 1) gave the lactams (3a-c).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (N.S.R.) is grateful to I.D.L., Hyderabad for the permission to carry out the work and the others (D.R. and K.V.R.) are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for research fellowships.

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Reaction of Lead(IV) Acetate with Steroidal Epoxides

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Manuscript received 31 July 1987, accepted 19 February 1988

IN continuation of our previous studies¹⁻³ on the reactions of lead(IV) acetate with steroidal compounds, we carried out the reaction of lead(IV)

acetate with 5,6 α -oxido-5 α -cholestane (1) and its 3 β -substituted analogues (2-4), which provided hydroxy acetates and diacetates (5-9). The structures of these compounds were established on the basis of spectral evidences. The compounds are useful for comparative chemical studies of steroidal compounds as derivatives.

1; X=H
2; X=Cl
3; X=OH
4; X=OAc

5; X=H
7; X=Cl

6; X=H
8; X=Cl

9

10

The epoxide (1)⁴ in acetic acid when treated with lead(IV) acetate provided the hydroxyacetate (5) and the diacetate (6) : *cholestan-5 α -hydroxy-6 β -acetate* (5; 30%) m.p. 104° (Found : C, 81.88; H, 11.01. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{49}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 81.9; H, 11.0%); ν_{max} 3 450 (br, 3°-OH), 1 735 (CH_3COO), 1 460 and 1 050 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); δ 4.5 (mc, $\text{C}_6\text{-}\alpha\text{H}$ $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz), 2.0 (3H, s, acetate protons), 1.1 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{10}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.75 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{13}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.90 and 0.85 (other methyl protons); *cholestan-5 α ,6 β -diacetate* (6; 20%), m.p. 150° (Found : C, 76.25; H, 10.65. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{47}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 76.3; H, 11.0%); ν_{max} 3 420 (br, 3°-OH), 1 735, 1 730 ($2\times\text{CH}_3\text{COO}$), 1 460 and 1 050 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); δ 4.6 (mc, $\text{C}_6\text{-}\alpha\text{H}$ $W_{1/2}$ 9 Hz), 2.0, 1.9 ($2\times$ 3H, s, acetate protons), 1.1 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{10}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.68 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{13}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.92 and 0.80 (other methyl protons).

Under similar reaction conditions the epoxides 2⁵ and 3-4⁶ provided 7-8 and 9-10, respectively. It is pertinent to mention that the epoxides 3 and 4 provided the same products 9⁸ and 10⁹ : *3 β -chloro-5 α -hydroxycholest-6 β -acetate*⁸ (7; 30%), m.p. 137° (Found : C, 72.4; H, 10.19. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{47}\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 72.4; H, 10.2%); positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 3 450 (br, 3°-OH), 1 735 (CH_3COO), 1 460 and 1 050 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); δ 5.4 (mc, $\text{C}_6\text{-}\alpha\text{H}$, $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz), 2.0 (3H, s, acetate protons), 1.28 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{10}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.68 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{13}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.92 and 0.80 (other methyl protons); *3 β -chloro-5 α ,6 β -diacetate*⁸ (8; 22.5%), m.p. 112° (Found : C, 71.49; H, 9.92. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{45}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 71.4; H, 9.9%); positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 1 740, 1 735 ($2\times\text{CH}_3\text{COO}$), 1 460, 1 050 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 760 cm^{-1} (CCl_4); δ 4.75 (mc, $\text{C}_6\text{-}\alpha\text{H}$, $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz), 2.0, 1.9 ($2\times$ 3H, s, acetate protons), 1.28 ($\text{C}_{10}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.68 ($\text{C}_{13}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.92 and 0.80 (other methyl protons); *3 β -5 α -diacetoxy-6 β -hydroxycholestane*⁹ (9; 25%), m.p. 96° (Found : C, 73.80; H, 10.32. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{53}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 73.8;

H, 10.3%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 410 (br, 3°-OH), 1 735, 1 740 (CH_3COO), 1 460 and 1 050 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 5.4 (mc, C6- α H, $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz), 2.0, 1.9 ($2 \times 3\text{H}$, s, acetate protons), 1.2 (C10- CH_3), 0.90 (C13- CH_3), 0.80 and 0.68 (other methyl protons); 3β -acetoxysteroid-5-ene⁹ (10; 30%), m.p. 116° (Found: C, 81.31; H, 11.21. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 81.3; H, 11.2%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 735 (CH_3COO), 1 625 (C=C), 1 460 and 1 050 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 5.45 (mc, C5 α H, $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz), 2.0 (3H, s, for acetate protons), 1.1 (C10- CH_3), 0.70 (C13- CH_3), 0.90 and 0.80 (other methyl protons).

Experimental

All m.ps. were observed on a Koflar apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were obtained on a Pye- Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A-60D instrument with Me_4Si as the internal standard. Tlc plates were coated with silica gel and sprayed with a aqueous 20% perchloric acid solution. Light petrol refers to a fraction having b.p. 60–80°. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

General procedure: A mixture of 5,6 α -oxido-5 α -cholestane (1; 2 g) in glacial acetic acid (150 ml) was refluxed with lead(IV) acetate for 8 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, diluted with ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (5%), water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvents gave an oil which was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with light petroleum ether-ether (1:3) yielded a solid which was recrystallised from methanol to yield 5 (600 mg, 30%), m.p. 104°.

Further elution with ether furnished 6 which was recrystallised from petrol (400 mg, 20%), m.p. 150°. Under the similar conditions, the 3 β -substituted-analogues (2–4) of 5,6 α -oxido-5 α -cholestane provided 7–10. The same amounts of reactants were used in each experiment.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. M. S. Ahmad, Chairman, Department of Chemistry for facilities.

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Syntheses of Steroidal Bromotetrazoles

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Manuscript received 28 December 1987, accepted 27 January 1988

RECENTLY, steroidal tetrazoles have become of interest on account of their pharmacological potentialities^{1–4}. This prompted us to synthesise α -bromo-substituted-steroidal tetrazoles (4–6) from sterically hindered bromoketones (1–3), such as 7 α -bromo-5 α -cholestan-6-one (1)⁵, 3 β -chloro-7 α -bromo-5 α -cholestan-6-one (2)⁵ and 3 β -acetoxysteroid-7 α -bromo-5 α -cholestan-6-one (3)⁶. α -Bromoketones 1, 2 and 3 on treatment with an excess of hydrazoic acid⁷ in the presence of BF_3 -etherate (as catalyst), furnished 6-aza-*B*-homo-7 α -bromo-5 α -cholestan[6,7-*d*]tetrazole (4), 3 β -chloro-6-aza-*B*-homo-7 α -bromo-5 α -cholestan[6,7-*d*]tetrazole (5) and 3 β -acetoxysteroid-6-aza-*B*-homo-7 α -bromo-5 α -cholestan[6,7-*d*]tetrazole (6), respectively. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral data.

Experimental

All melting points were determined on a Kofler's block apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye- Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A-60D instrument using TMS as internal standard. Light petroleum refers to the fraction b.p. 40–60°.

Reaction of 7 α -bromo-5 α -cholestan-6-one (1) with hydrazoic acid BF_3 -etherate: A solution of α -bromoketone (1; 2 g) in benzene (25 ml) was added during 5 h to a mixture of hydrazoic acid in benzene and freshly distilled borontrifluoride etherate (2 ml) maintained at 0°. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand at room temperature for 3 days. Thereafter it was washed with sodium